

[Spin-Ion Technologies](#), a spin-off company from Paris-Saclay University and the French National Center for Scientific Research (CNRS), specializes in developing advanced ion beam processes for the semiconductor industry. Established in 2017, the company focuses on engineering magnetic materials at the atomic scale to enhance the performance of spintronic devices, such as magnetic memory, sensors, and neuromorphic circuits.

The company’s mission is to reduce the power consumption of various magnetic devices, including magneto-resistive random-access memory (MRAM) and neuromorphic computing integrated circuits (ICs). Both MRAM and neuromorphic ICs are emerging markets poised for vigorous growth in the coming years.

MRAM REVENUE FORECAST, IN \$M – FROM 2019 TO 2029

Source: Emerging Non-Volatile Memory 2024 | Report | www.yolegroup.com

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According to [Yole Group’s](#) annual report, [Emerging Non-Volatile Memory 2024](#), the MRAM market, valued at \$80 million in 2023, is expected to grow to more than \$780 million by 2029, driven primarily by embedded applications such as code and data storage in microcontrollers (MCUs), low-power IoTs, wearables, and edge-AI devices. Yole Group has also investigated the neuromorphic IC market opportunity and highlighted a total addressable market of more than \$8 billion by 2034. The complete analysis is available in the recent [Neuromorphic Computing, Memory and Sensing 2024](#) report.

Simone Bertolazzi, Principal Analyst at Yole Group, talked with **Corina Numbela, CEO & Co-Founder of Spin-Ion Technologies**, to learn more about her company’s innovative work, recent developments, and future goals.

Discover the details of their conversation below.

Simone Bertolazzi (SB): Please introduce Spin-Ion Technologies and its core mission to our readers.

Corina Numbela (CN): Founded in 2017 and based at the Nanosciences and Nanotechnologies Center (CNRS)

at Paris-Saclay, Spin-Ion Technologies is an innovative French company specializing in using ion beam solutions to enhance the performance of commercial magnetic devices. Spin-Ion focuses on three fast-growing markets: magnetic sensors, memory devices (MRAM), and neuromorphic chips for edge AI.

Spin-Ion Technologies combines cutting-edge research in ion beam solutions with innovation in magnetic device technology to meet the growing demands for more efficient semiconductor chips. Our innovations aim to improve sensor accuracy, memory density, and artificial intelligence capabilities at the edge, enabling the development of smarter, more responsive, energy-efficient, and cost-effective technological solutions.

Helium-S: This system utilizes an ultra-compact and ultra-fast He^+ ion beam facility to enable precise manipulation of magnetic properties – Courtesy of Spin Ion, 2024

SB: What are the primary applications of your ion-beam processes in the semiconductor industry?

CN: Our ion-beam processes are really versatile, compatible with current manufacturing processes, and have a huge impact across the semiconductor industry. Our solution enables more efficient spintronic devices and integration of on-chip multi-functionalities to address, in particular, the challenges of edge computing. In the world of edge AI, our technology is making a big difference by enabling smarter, more energy-efficient, responsive, and adaptive systems for applications in IoT, industry, automotive, smart cities, mobility, and health monitoring.

SB: How does your technology enhance the performance of spintronic devices?

CN: Spin-Ion's process employs an He^+ ion beam technology to precisely engineer the structure of magnetic materials at the atomic scale. Since most of the magnetic properties of current spintronic devices depend on the

atomic arrangement at interfaces, this technology allows for the very precise tuning of the magnetic properties. The key benefits are the post-growth engineering of magnetic properties on demand, reduced variability at the material and device level, and the possibility of inducing spatial variation of magnetic properties by ion beam treatment through a lithographic mask.

SB: What are the main challenges that the industry faces in engineering magnetic materials at the atomic scale?

CN: Engineering magnetic materials at the atomic scale presents key challenges. One of the most significant challenges concerns variability issues at small technological nodes. In particular, magnetic tunnel junctions (MTJs), which are essential in spintronic applications, consist of up to 20 different ultra-thin layers, some only a few atomic planes thick. Disorder at the atomic level, such as interface intermixing, roughness, or variations in crystalline texture, cause spatial fluctuations in magnetic properties. Additionally, fabrication techniques like ion beam etching can induce edge damage in MTJ arrays, further contributing to variability in magnetic properties. This variability affects performance, reliability, and efficiency, limiting the density and scalability of spintronic devices.

SB: Can you discuss any recent breakthroughs or innovations your company has achieved?

CN: Through our processes, we achieve significantly faster crystallization of MTJs with lower annealing temperatures, resulting in lower defect rates at the material level, surpassing conventional thermal annealing methods at high temperatures, and gaining advantages in thermal budget management.

Another key benefit of our technology is the possibility of reducing edge damage induced by the fabrication process in large arrays of spintronic devices such as STT-MRAM.

Finally, using ion irradiation through a mask enables the fabrication of chips integrating different magnetic properties, opening the path to smarter neuromorphic chips for edge AI computing.

Illustration of a chip irradiated with the Spin Ion Technologies process, optimized to modify material properties

by ion irradiation – Courtesy of Spin Ion, 2024

SB: What specific advancements has Spin-Ion Technologies made in the field of neuromorphic computing?

CN: By leveraging our patented ion beam process to customize magnetic tunnel junctions, we are currently developing a novel analog in-memory computing architecture that mimics the synaptic metaplasticity of the human brain. Our technology overcomes both catastrophic forgetting and reduces device variability, two major challenges in current AI hardware, especially for edge applications. By enabling a unique spintronic synapse architecture and continuous learning on-chip, Spin-Ion technologies will transform edge computing by drastically reducing latency and power consumption compared to traditional architectures. We will pave the way for the next generation of smarter AI applications, including smart cities, healthcare, consumer electronics, automotive, and industrial automation.

SB: What are the most important collaborations or partnerships that Spin-Ion Technologies has established with academic institutions and industrial companies?

CN: Our customers and stakeholders span a diverse range of industries, including semiconductor manufacturers, research institutions, AI hardware developers, and end-users in various sectors such as IoT, healthcare, consumer electronics, automotive, and industrial automation. They are all seeking advanced, energy-efficient solutions for edge AI applications and next-generation memory technologies. This is validated by the strong endorsement of our technology and its commercial potential, evidenced by our early traction, including pay services, ongoing Joint Development Agreements (JDAs), and Proofs of Concept (POCs) projects.

SB: What are your company's goals and priorities for the next five years?

CN: We have developed our ion beam technology to be flexible and applicable to various spintronic devices, including MRAM, magnetic sensors, and neuromorphic computing chips and their future generation. This flexibility allows us to address multiple market segments and applications, scaling our business across diverse industry verticals. In the next five years, we will target rapidly expanding markets in neuromorphic computing, magnetic sensors, and MRAM. We have built a strong portfolio of patents and trade secrets enabling us to pursue multiple licensing agreements across various applications and customers. We maintain an active R&D program to continuously improve our technology and develop new applications. This ongoing innovation supports long-term scalability by creating new licensing opportunities and maintaining our competitive edge in the market.

SB: Do you have any final thoughts or messages to share with our readers?

CN: We envision becoming the global leader in ion beam solutions for spintronic technologies, driving innovation in the semiconductor industry. By 2030, we aim to establish our technology as a manufacturing standard, enabling more efficient and powerful IoT/edge applications dedicated to healthcare, consumer electronics, industrial automation, and smart cities.